

Structural Poisson bracket for Hamilton system on \mathbb{R}^{2n} based on generalized structural Poisson bracket theory on \mathbb{R}^r

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Abstract

In this paper, inspired by the generalized structural Poisson bracket (GSPB) for the generalized covariant Hamilton system (GCHS) on \mathbb{R}^r , we reconsider the Poisson bracket for Hamilton system on \mathbb{R}^{2n} , we generalize the Poisson bracket for a generalization of Hamilton system on \mathbb{R}^{2n} . Meanwhile, the geometric bracket on \mathbb{R}^{2n} also emerges. As an application, we consider the canonical commutation relation in different cases.

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1 Introduction

Classical Hamilton system (HS) theory is defined in even-dimensional phase space corresponding to the classical Poisson bracket (PB or CPB) ¹. Although this structure has good properties, it also limits its application. Many of the special properties of Hamiltonian systems are formulated in terms of the Poisson bracket operator, so this operator plays a central role in the theory developed here. Therefore, scientists [1, 2] have been trying to popularize the classical Hamilton mechanics theory. A generalized theory of Hamilton system is called generalized Hamilton system (GHS). Later, scientists used generalized Poisson bracket (GPB) to define generalized Hamilton system (GHS), which is more concise and convenient, thus promoting the further development of Hamilton mechanics. Generalized Hamilton system (GHS) dynamics plays an important role in many fields of science and technology [3]. It has been widely valued in mathematics, mechanics, physics, engineering science and many other fields. It has made a series of important progress in theory, calculation and application. However, its basic theoretical framework is not perfect, and much work remains to be further studied [4, 5]. Recently, [6] has developed the generalized Poisson bracket (GPB) for the generalized Hamilton system (GHS) on \mathbb{R}^r , it obtains the generalized structural Poisson bracket (GSPB) for the generalized covariant Hamilton system (GCHS) on \mathbb{R}^r as a complete theory to solve some left questions of GHS. Later, we have considered the generalized covariant Hamilton system in complex coordinates [7]. In this paper, we try to construct the following relation image between different brackets in different dimensions associated with different application.

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 PB(CPB) & \rightarrow & GPB \\
 \downarrow & & \downarrow \\
 SPB & \rightarrow & GSPB
 \end{array}$$

and different Hamiltonian system defined by corresponding Poisson brackets in an intrinsic relation can be given by

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 HS & \rightarrow & GHS \\
 \downarrow & & \downarrow \\
 CHS & \rightarrow & GCHS
 \end{array}$$

2 Preliminaries

2.1 Classical Poisson bracket and classical Hamilton system

\mathbb{R} denotes the field of real numbers, \mathbb{C} the complex field, and \mathbb{F} either \mathbb{R} or \mathbb{C} . \mathbb{F}^n denotes the space of all n -dimensional vectors, and, unless otherwise stated, all vectors

¹ PB: Poisson bracket; GPB: Generalized Poisson bracket;
 SPB: Structural Poisson Bracket;
 GHS: Generalized Hamilton System; TGHS: thorough generalized Hamiltonian system

are column vectors. Functions are real and smooth unless otherwise stated; smooth means C^∞ or real analytic.

The classical Poisson bracket defined on functions on \mathbb{R}^{2n} is [4]

$$\{f_1, f_2\}_{CPB} = \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial f_1}{\partial q_i} \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial p_i} - \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial p_i} \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial q_i} \right), \quad \forall f_j \in C^\infty(M, \mathbb{R})$$

By using CPB, it follows the classical Hamilton system [3–5]

$$\dot{q}_i = \{q_i, H\}_{CPB}, \quad \dot{p}_i = \{p_i, H\}_{CPB}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n \quad (1)$$

where $\dot{q}_i = \frac{d}{dt}q_i$. The variable t denotes a real scalar variable called time, and the symbol \cdot is used for d/dt . Meanwhile, the canonical commutation relation in terms of the CPB follows

$$\{q_j, p_i\}_{CPB} = \delta_{ij} \quad (2)$$

The variables q and p are said to be conjugate variables: p is conjugate to q .

2.2 Generalized Poisson bracket

Many of the properties of Hamiltonian systems are formulated in terms of the generalized Poisson bracket operator, so this operator plays a central role in the theory developed here. Thus, the GPB is defined as the bilinear operation [4–6]

$$\{f, g\}_{GPB} = \nabla^T f J \nabla g = J_{ij} \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial g}{\partial x_j}$$

on \mathbb{R}^r , where structural matrix J satisfies antisymmetric $J_{ij} = \{x_i, x_j\}_{GPB} = -J_{ji}$. Clearly $\{f, g\}_{GPB}$ is a smooth map, and one can easily verify that $\{, \}_{GPB}$ is skew-symmetric and bilinear. A little tedious calculation verifies Jacobi's identity. For simplicity, let's denote

$$N_{CC}[f, g, h] = \{f, \{g, h\}_{GPB}\}_{GPB} + \{g, \{h, f\}_{GPB}\}_{GPB} + \{h, \{f, g\}_{GPB}\}_{GPB}$$

The GPB has the following important properties [5, 6]:

1. Antisymmetry: $\{F, G\}_{GPB} = -\{G, F\}_{GPB}$
2. Bilinearity: $\{\lambda F + \mu G, K\}_{GPB} = \lambda \{F, K\}_{GPB} + \mu \{G, K\}_{GPB}$
3. Jacobi identity: $N_{CC}[F, G, H] = 0$
4. Leibnitz identity: $\{F \cdot G, K\}_{GPB} = F \cdot \{G, K\}_{GPB} + G \cdot \{F, K\}_{GPB}$
5. Non-degeneration: if for $F, \{F, G\}_{GPB} = 0$, then G must be a constant.

where F, G, K are elements in $C^\infty(P)$, λ, μ are arbitrary real number.

Generalized Poisson bracket (GPB) can be defined by the first four properties above.

Definition 1. [5, 6] *The generalized Poisson bracket on the smooth manifold M is an operation on the smooth function space $C^\infty(M)$, for $F, G \in C^\infty(M)$, it exists $\{F, G\}_{GPB} \in C^\infty(M)$, the operation satisfies the condition 1 – 4, $(M, \{, \}_{GPB})$ is correspondingly called Poisson manifolds.*

Definition 2. [4–6] *The skew-symmetric matrix $J = (J_{ij}(x))$ of order $m \times m$ is called structural matrix of the GPB on M , where $J_{ij}(x) = \{x_i, x_j\}_{GPB}$.*

2.3 Generalized Hamiltonian system

Generalized Hamiltonian system (GHS) is defined as [3, 5, 6]

$$\dot{x} = \frac{dx}{dt} = J(x) \nabla H(x), \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^m$$

where $J(x)$ is structure matrix, $\nabla H(x)$ is the gradient of the function Hamilton. Equivalently, Hamiltonian equations can be further written as

$$\{x_i, H\}_{GPB} = J_{ij} \frac{\partial H}{\partial x_j}$$

1. when structural matrix $J(x) = J_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & I_n \\ -I_n & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ holds, then the system is the classical Hamilton system (CHS).
2. When the structural matrix element is a homogeneous linear function of x , namely, $J_{ij} = c_{ij}^k x_k$, the corresponding Poisson bracket is Lie-Poisson bracket.
3. The dimension of classical Hamilton's structure matrix must be even dimension, and the generalized Hamilton can be arbitrary dimension.

3 The GSPB on \mathbb{R}^r and geometric bracket

Let M be a smooth manifold and let s be a smooth real structural function on M which is completely determined by the structure of manifold M . Without loss of generality, we give the definition of generalized structural Poisson bracket in a abstract covariant form,

3.1 The GSPB and geometric bracket

Theorem 1 (GSPB). [6] *The GSPB on M of two functions $f, g \in C^\infty(M, \mathbb{R})$ is defined as*

$$\{f, g\} = \{f, g\}_{GPB} + G(s, f, g)$$

for \mathbb{R}^r , the geometric bracket is

$$G(s, f, g) = f\{s, g\}_{GPB} - g\{s, f\}_{GPB}$$

where s is structural function associated with M .

The GSPB

$$\begin{aligned} \{f, g\} &= \{f, g\}_{GPB} + G(s, f, g) \\ &= \{f, g\}_{GPB} + f\{s, g\}_{GPB} - g\{s, f\}_{GPB} \end{aligned}$$

which depends smoothly on both $\{f, g\}_{GPB}$ and the geobacket $G(s, f, g)$.

Let's denote

$$N_{CL}[f, g, h] = \{f, \{g, h\}\} + \{g, \{h, f\}\} + \{h, \{f, g\}\}$$

for convenience.

Proposition 1. For all $f, g, h \in C^\infty(M, \mathbb{R})$, $\lambda, \mu \in \mathbb{R}$, the GSPB 1 has the following important properties

1. skew-symmetry: $\{f, g\} = -\{g, f\}$.
2. Bilinearity: $\{\lambda f + \mu g, h\} = \lambda \{f, h\} + \mu \{g, h\}$.
3. Generalized Jacobi identity (GJI): $N_{CL}[f, g, h] = 0$.
4. Generalized Leibnitz identity: $\{fg, h\} = \{fg, h\}_{GPB} + G(s, fg, h)$.
5. Non degeneracy: if for all f , $\{f, g\} = 0$, then $\{f, g\}_{GPB} = G(s, g, f)$.

Definition 3. The generalized structural Poisson bracket on the smooth manifold M is an operation on the smooth function space $C^\infty(M)$, for $F, G \in C^\infty(M)$, it exists $\{F, G\} = \{F, G\}_{GPB} + G(s, F, G) \in C^\infty(M)$, the operation satisfies the condition 1 – 4, $(M, \{, \})$ is correspondingly called generalized Poisson manifolds.

By the GSPB, we can define covariant equilibrium equation which is different from classic theory stated.

Definition 4. The GSPB is said to be a covariant equilibrium equation if it satisfies

$$\{f, g\} = \{f, g\}_{GPB} + G(s, f, g) = 0$$

for $f, g \in C^\infty(M, \mathbb{R})$.

Proposition 2. The skew-symmetric matrix $W = (W_{ij}(x))$ of order $m \times m$ is called structural matrix of the GSPB on M , where $W_{ij}(x) = \{x_i, x_j\}$.

Note that proposition 2 is the revision of the definition 2,

$$W_{kl} = \{x_k, x_l\} = J_{kl} + G(s, x_k, x_l)$$

where $G(s, x_k, x_l) = \mathcal{J}_{kl}$ is the geobacket,

3.2 Geometric bracket

In generally, as 1 abstractly given

$$\{f, g\} = \{f, g\}_{GPB} + G(s, f, g)$$

previously, the geobacket $G(s, f, g)$ is just a part of the GSPB as a correct term, and it surely fulfils some basic properties it owns. By doing an operator transformation, we have successfully confirmed an accurate expression for the geobacket. In this section, the geobacket will be discussed for more details. The geobacket has the form generated by the GPB,

$$G(s, f, g) = f\{s, g\}_{GPB} - g\{s, f\}_{GPB}$$

The most different place is that the geobacket contains three variables f, g, s , the structure variable s is the key to the GSPB. In the other hand, the fact that the geobacket is skew-symmetric $G(s; f, g) = -G(s; g, f)$, and some properties also holds as follows

$$G(s, f, f) = G(s, s, s) = 0$$

$$\begin{aligned} G(s, s, g) &= s\{s, g\}_{GPB} \\ G(s, f, s) &= s\{f, s\}_{GPB} \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Consider $g = H$ in general, then the geobacket turns to the form with respect to the Hamiltonian system

$$G(s, f, H) = f\{s, H\}_{GPB} - H\{s, f\}_{GPB}$$

or citing the theorem 2, it becomes

$$G(s, f, H) = -H\{s, f\}_{GPB} + wf$$

If the geobacket disappears, that is to say, $G(s, f, H) = 0$ or $H\{s, f\}_{GPB} = wf$, then the GCHS is reduced to the GHS as known.

3.3 Generalized covariant Hamilton system

In view of the results of the previous sections, it would seem that the next question to be considered is the GSPB for corresponding to a new more general Hamiltonian system. This is one of the central and difficult questions in a new framework of geometric Hamiltonian system.

As the GHS stated, the GPB defines the GHS, and in other words, the GHS is closely relied on the GPB. We will follow this thoughts to study the extension of the GHS fundamentally, namely, the GSPB will give a new generalized Hamilton system, we call it generalized covariant Hamilton system. According to the 1, we can abstractly obtain the covariant form of the GCHS in terms of the GSPB

$$\{f, H\} = \{f, H\}_{GPB} + G(s, f, H)$$

by replacing the function g to the Hamiltonian function H in 1, transparently, the geobacket $G(s, f, H)$ is a correct term which never appears before for the GPB. As we accurately found a specific expression for this abstract covariant form of the geobacket $G(s, f, g)$, then it can be studied more precisely in the form

$$G(s, f, g) = f\{s, g\}_{GPB} - g\{s, f\}_{GPB}$$

We will discuss the GCHS based on the GSPB 1. The GCHS follows directly from the theorem 1. Namely, the GSPB [4] in details is given by

$$\{f, g\} = \{f, g\}_{GPB} + G(s, f, g)$$

It can be written as a system of one equation by introducing the structure variable s , the GPB $\{f, g\}_{GPB}$ and the geobacket $G(s, f, g)$. A nonlinear mechanical system that gives rise to this equation is a complete system. It can fundamentally solve a prime question that a nonlinear system can always be expressed as a generalized covariant Hamilton system, in other words, under the full description of structure variable s it can be expressed as a generalized covariant Hamilton system. Hence, the so-called Hamiltonian realization can be figured out by the GSPB. More importantly, such GSPB is complete and remedies the incomplete of the GPB. A Hamiltonian system is complete if and only if it admits the geobacket $G(s, f, g)$.

As known, the Hamiltonian H is the total energy of a physical system. In the conservative case when H is independent of t . As a result, for the GSPB, by taking the $g = H$, it yields a series of output of Hamiltonian system [4]

$$\{f, H\} = \{f, H\}_{GPB} + G(s, f, H)$$

This can be certainly called the covariant evolution. It can be split into two dynamical parts

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{df}{dt} &= \dot{f} = \{f, H\}_{GPB} - H\{s, f\}_{GPB} \\ w &= \{s, H\}_{GPB} \end{aligned}$$

One can give a specific reason why the S-dynamics can be a dynamic form. Accordingly, if let $f = s$ be given intentionally, then a precise result holds $\frac{ds}{dt} = w = \{s, H\}_{GPB}$. Based on the GSPB, the covariant evolution emerges accordingly.

Theorem 2 (TGHS,S-dynamics, GCHS). *Based on the GSPB for Hamiltonian H , then*

TGHS: $\frac{df}{dt} = \dot{f} = \{f, H\}_{GPB} - H\{s, f\}_{GPB}$.

S-dynamics: $\frac{ds}{dt} = w = \{s, H\}_{GPB} = \{1, H\}$.

GCHS: $\frac{Df}{dt} = \{f, H\} = \{f, H\}_{GPB} + G(s, f, H)$.

By defining the GSPB which can basically solve and describe an entire Hamiltonian system, even nonlinear system.

Corollary 1. *The covariant equilibrium equation of the GCHS is $\frac{Df}{dt} = \{f, H\} = 0$ such that equation*

$$\{f, H\}_{GPB} + G(s, f, H) = 0$$

holds on the manifolds M .

Corollary 2. *The generalized force field F on the generalized Poisson manifold $(P, S, \{\cdot, \cdot\})$ is shown as*

$$F = \frac{d}{dt}p = -DH$$

Its components is $F_k = \dot{p}_k = -D_k H$.

Theorem 3. *There exists two different canonical Hamilton equations on manifolds respectively given by*

Canonical thorough Hamilton equations

$$\frac{dx_k}{dt} = \dot{x}_k = J_{kj} D_j H, \quad \frac{dp_k}{dt} = \dot{p}_k = -D_k H$$

canonical covariant Hamilton equations

$$\frac{Dx_k}{dt} = \{x_k, H\}, \quad \frac{Dp_k}{dt} = \{p_k, H\}$$

where $\{\cdot, \cdot\} = \{\cdot, \cdot\}_{GPB} + G(s, \cdot, \cdot)$ is generalized structure Poisson bracket, $D_i = \partial_i + \partial_i s$ is generalized derivative operators.

There is an equilibrium condition of the TGHS that satisfies equations $\frac{df}{dt} = \dot{f} = 0$, namely, it equals $\{f, H\}_{GPB} = H\{s, f\}_{GPB}$. The same procedure goes for the GCHS that the equilibrium condition holds as $\frac{Df}{dt} = \{f, H\} = 0$, equivalently, the equation is given by

$$\{f, H\}_{GPB} + G(s, f, H) = 0$$

It's treated as the covariant equilibrium condition $\{f, H\}_{GPB} = -G(s, f, H)$ for the GCHS that is covariant steady state for the matter as corollary 1 indicated.

Corollary 3. *By corollary 2, canonical thorough Hamilton equations (CTHE) can be simply rewritten as*

$$\frac{dx_k}{dt} = \dot{x}_k = J_{jk}F_j, \quad \frac{dp_k}{dt} = \dot{p}_k = F_k$$

The canonical covariant Hamilton equations can be precisely written in the form

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{Dx_k}{dt} &= \{x_k, H\} = J_{kj}\partial_j H + x_k w - H b_k \\ \frac{Dp_k}{dt} &= \{p_k, H\} = -\partial_k H + p_k w - H A_k \end{aligned}$$

Obviously, this canonical covariant Hamilton equations nicely embodies the GSPB theory

Corollary 4. *The geometric canonical commutation relation is rewritten as*

$$\{x_j, p_k\} = \delta_{jk} + x_j A_k + p_k b_j = \delta_{jk} + (x_j, p_k) \begin{pmatrix} A_k \\ b_j \end{pmatrix}$$

where $\{\cdot, \cdot\}$ is the GSPB.

4 Structural Poisson bracket on \mathbb{R}^{2n}

Under the inspiration of the construction of the GSPB, we can consider the more general form of the CPB on \mathbb{R}^{2n} . We always suppose that there exists a scalar function $\varphi = \varphi(q, p) \in C^\infty(M, \mathbb{R})$ defined on phase space, and $\varphi = \varphi(q, p)$ is only given by the intrinsic structure of the phase space, where $q = (q_1, \dots, q_n)$, $p = (p_1, \dots, p_n)$.

Definition 5. *The structural Poisson bracket of two functions $f, g \in C^\infty(M, \mathbb{R})$ is defined as*

$$\{f, g\}_{SPB} = \{f, g\}_{CPB} + G(\varphi, f, g) \quad (4)$$

for \mathbb{R}^{2n} , and $G(\varphi, f, g)$ is the geobacket.

Hence, this section will extend the CPB to more general form which is called the SPB on \mathbb{R}^{2n} by introducing a transformation.

Theorem 4. *The SPB on \mathbb{R}^{2n} is*

$$\{f_1, f_2\}_{SPB} = \{f_1, f_2\}_{CPB} + G(\varphi, f_1, f_2), \quad \forall f_j \in C^\infty(M, \mathbb{R})$$

and the geobacket appears formally as

$$G(\varphi, f_1, f_2) = f_1\{\varphi, f_2\}_{CPB} - f_2\{\varphi, f_1\}_{CPB}$$

Proof. Let a transformation be given below

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial q_i} \rightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial q_i} + \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial q_i}, \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial p_i} \rightarrow \frac{\partial}{\partial p_i} + \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial p_i}$$

for the classical Poisson bracket defined on \mathbb{R}^{2n} , it obeys the same rule as the GSPB does, precisely, the general form SPB which extends the CPB is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \{f_1, f_2\}_{SPB} &= \sum_i \left(\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial q_i} f_1 + f_1 \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial q_i} \right) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial p_i} f_2 + f_2 \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial p_i} \right) - \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial p_i} f_1 + f_1 \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial p_i} \right) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial q_i} f_2 + f_2 \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial q_i} \right) \right) \\ &= \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial q_i} f_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial p_i} f_2 - \frac{\partial}{\partial p_i} f_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial q_i} f_2 \right) + f_1 \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial q_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial p_i} f_2 - \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial p_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial q_i} f_2 \right) \\ &\quad + f_2 \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial q_i} f_1 \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial p_i} - \frac{\partial}{\partial p_i} f_1 \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial q_i} \right) \\ &= \{f_1, f_2\}_{CPB} + f_1 \{\varphi, f_2\}_{CPB} - f_2 \{\varphi, f_1\}_{CPB} \end{aligned}$$

where φ is the structural function that represents the manifolds only linked to the structure of manifolds M . \square

Obviously, the SPB appears on \mathbb{R}^{2n} and shows as GSPB does on \mathbb{R}^r , as we mention, the SPB and GSPB remain the same in the form. Notice that the bracket that has been generalized keeps the same form as the other methods do. In an effort to extend the applicable field of the CPB, structural functions are rationally introduced in order to extend the scope of application of the CPB that is already be proposed. Usually the properties of new bracket that are developed in advanced thoughts on manifolds and are similar to the classical theory, but much of the basic properties follow from the elementary ideas in Hamiltonian system. Here one fact is presented. As already known, most of which follow from the fact that the equations of motion can be written as a Hamiltonian system.

4.1 Covariant Hamiltonian system

For simplicity, let's abbreviate and simplify some notations: First, we set forth basic notation.

- CHS: Covariant Hamiltonian system
- THS: Thorough Hamiltonian system
- SPB: Structural Poisson bracket

Theorem 5 (THS,S-dynamics, CHS). *Based on the SPB for Hamiltonian H , then*

THS: $\frac{df}{dt} = \dot{f} = \{f, H\}_{CPB} - H\{\varphi, f\}_{CPB}$.

S-dynamics: $\frac{d\varphi}{dt} = w = \{\varphi, H\}_{CPB} = \{1, H\}$.

CHS: $\frac{Df}{dt} = \{f, H\}_{SPB} = \{f, H\}_{CPB} + G(\varphi, f, H)$.

hold on \mathbb{R}^{2n} .

As a consequence of this point, let $f_2 = H$ be given, then the covariant evolution equation in terms of the variable f_1 that is more general than the classical equation can be shown as

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}f_1}{dt} = \{f_1, H\}_{SPB} = \{f_1, H\}_{CPB} + G(\varphi, f_1, H) \quad (5)$$

is called covariant Hamiltonian system (CHS), where the THS is defined as

$$\frac{df_1}{dt} = \dot{f}_1 = \{f_1, H\}_{CPB} - H\{\varphi, f_1\}_{CPB}$$

and the S-dynamics follows that can be formally imitated and defined as

$$w = \{\varphi, H\}_{CPB} = \{1, H\}_{SPB} = \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial q_i} \frac{\partial H}{\partial p_i} - \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial p_i} \frac{\partial H}{\partial q_i} \right) \quad (6)$$

Specifically, the covariant evolution equation in terms of the variables q_i , p_i can be theoretically obtained

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\mathcal{D}q_i}{dt} &= \{q_i, H\}_{SPB} = \{q_i, H\}_{CPB} + G(\varphi, q_i, H) \\ \frac{\mathcal{D}p_i}{dt} &= \{p_i, H\}_{SPB} = \{p_i, H\}_{CPB} + G(\varphi, p_i, H), \quad i = 1, \dots, n \end{aligned}$$

A generalized covariant Hamiltonian system is a system of $2n$ ordinary differential equations of the form. Accordingly, the THS can be rewritten as in terms of the coordinates q_i and the momentum p_i

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dq_i}{dt} &= \dot{q}_i = \{q_i, H\}_{CPB} - H\{\varphi, q_i\}_{CPB} \\ \frac{dp_i}{dt} &= \dot{p}_i = \{p_i, H\}_{CPB} - H\{\varphi, p_i\}_{CPB}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, let $f_1 = \varphi$ be given in the Eq(5), then let us check the properties of the structure function φ out, equation for φ holds as

$$\frac{\mathcal{D}\varphi}{dt} = \{\varphi, H\}_{SPB} = \{\varphi, H\}_{CPB} + G(\varphi, \varphi, H)$$

Substituting the Eq(6) into above equation, then $\{\varphi, H\} = w + \varphi w = (1 + \varphi)w$, it well fits the covariant evolution equation, and it also reveals that S-dynamics comes from the fact, that is to say, it equals the time derivative of φ

$$\frac{d\varphi}{dt} = w = \{\varphi, H\}_{CPB}$$

Thus, that is what this structural variable represents a dynamic system.

Notice that if the CPB is replaced by the GPB, then the CHS becomes GCHS, the SPB turns to the GSPB, accordingly, and a series of changes appear in procedure.

5 Geometric canonical commutation relation

This section will give geometric canonical commutation relation by using the GSPB, the geobacket $G(s, x_j, p_k)$ will derive new term as a correct term for the classic result, namely, new terms are indeed from the geobacket. For this purpose, we firstly define a new sign function similar to the kronecker delta.

In conclusions, the CPB and the GPB are leading to the same consequence, that is,

$$\begin{aligned}\{q_j, p_i\}_{CPB} &= \delta_{ij} \\ \{x_m, p_n\}_{GPB} &= \delta_{mn}\end{aligned}$$

and for the SPB in terms of q_m, p_i , we have

$$\begin{aligned}\{q_m, p_i\}_{SPB} &= \delta_{qm} + G(\varphi, q_m, p_i), \\ G(\varphi, q_m, p_i) &= q_m \partial_i \varphi + p_m \partial_{p_i} \varphi\end{aligned}$$

In like wise, for the GSPB, it leads to the desired result

$$\begin{aligned}\{x_j, p_k\} &\equiv \{x_j, p_k\}_{GSPB} = \delta_{jk} + G(s, x_j, p_k) \\ G(s, x_j, p_k) &= x_j \partial_k s + p_k J_{jq} \partial_q s\end{aligned}$$

Theory	Formula	Scalar function
PB (CPB)	$\{f_1, f_2\}_{CPB} = \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial f_1}{\partial q_i} \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial p_i} - \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial p_i} \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial q_i} \right), \quad \forall f_j \in C^\infty(M, \mathbb{R})$	0
GPB	$\{f, g\}_{GPB} = \nabla^T f J \nabla g = J_{ij} \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial g}{\partial x_j}$	0
SPB	$\{f_1, f_2\}_{SPB} = \{f_1, f_2\}_{CPB} + f_1 \{\varphi, f_2\}_{CPB} - f_2 \{\varphi, f_1\}_{CPB}$	φ
GSPB	$\{f, g\} = \{f, g\}_{GPB} + G(s, f, g)$	s

Table 1: different Poisson brackets

Obviously, with the geobacket, we fulfill a more complete theory to more wider range of application.

6 Conclusions

Theory	Formula	S-dyanmcis
HS	$\dot{q}_i = \{q_i, H\}_{CPB}, \quad \dot{p}_i = \{p_i, H\}_{CPB}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n$	0
GHS	$\dot{x}_i = \{x_i, H\}_{GPB} = J_{ij} \frac{\partial H}{\partial x_j}$	0
CHS	$\frac{\mathcal{D}f}{dt} = \{f, H\}_{SPB} = \{f, H\}_{CPB} + G(\varphi, f, H)$	$w = \{\varphi, H\}_{CPB} = \{1, H\}_{SPB}$
GCHS	$\frac{\mathcal{D}f}{dt} = \{f, H\} = \{f, H\}_{GPB} + G(s, f, H)$	$w = \{s, H\}_{GPB} = \{1, H\}$

Table 2: different Hamiltonian system

In conclusions, as we can see, the theory of Hamiltonian systems is a vast subject that can be studied from many different viewpoints, but it has flaws for practical

application, then it has to be further developments. This paper completely develops the basic theory of Hamiltonian differential equations from a dynamical systems point of view. This paper defines a covariant Hamiltonian system of ordinary differential equations, gives some basic results about such systems, and presents several concepts.

Essentially, each different bracket corresponds to a Hamiltonian mechanical system, as a consequence,

$$PB(CPB) \rightarrow HS$$

$$GPB \rightarrow GHS$$

$$SPB \rightarrow CHS$$

$$GSPB \rightarrow GCHS$$

Note that

$$PB(CPB) \rightarrow HS$$

$$GPB \rightarrow GHS$$

leads to the similar result, there is no essential change in formulations, but in different dimensions. Conversely, for the extensions of their theories, we have the geometric bracket introduced to above theories, it revises those restrained theories to a more general form

$$SPB \rightarrow CHS$$

$$GSPB \rightarrow GCHS$$

We have introduced an geometric approach to solving Hamiltonian mechanical problems based on the generalized structural Poisson bracket formulation. As a matter of fact, there always exists a structural function s or φ such that geometric bracket $G(s, f, g)$ or $G(\varphi, f, g)$ holds for the GSPB or SPB and the GCHS or CHS on manifolds or \mathbb{R}^{2n} .

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